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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FAST DISPERSIBLE TABLETS OF CITALOPRAM HYDROBROMIDE

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ABSTRACT

A Fast dispersible tablets disintegrate either rapidly in the oral cavity without the need of water or chewing. Citalopram hydrobromide is a highly selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor with minimal norepinephrine and dopamine neuronal reuptake and Tolerance to the 5-HT selective inhibitor. It is frequently used off-label to treat anxiety greatly reduce the symptoms of diabetic neuropathy and premature ejaculation and effective in the treatment of post- stroke pathological crying. It is estimated that 12% of the population affected by this problem. In order to calm the anxiety disorder the present study was aimed to formulate fast dispersible tablets to resolve the difficulties of pediatric and geriatric patients. The tablets were prepared by direct compression method using different superdisintegrants with different concentration such as Crosscarmellose sodium, crospovidone and sodium starch glycolate for their suitability in terms of drug release efficiency. 12 formulations having superdisintegrants alone and its combination at different concentrations (7.5, 10, 12.5 mg) were prepared. Effect of superdisintegrant on wetting time, dispersion time, drug content and *in vitro* release has been studied. Tablet containing crosscarmellose sodium showed excellent *in vitro* dispersion time and drug release as compared to other formulations. After study of nine formulations CP4 to CP6 showed fast dispersion time and maximum drug release in 7min and 5 min respectively. It was concluded that the fast-dispersible Citalopram tablets could be prepared by direct compression method using crosscarmellose sodium superdisintegrants for effective therapy

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INTRODUCTION

The tablet is the most widely used dosage form because of its convenience in terms of self-administration, compactness, and ease in manufacturing. For the past one decade, there has been an enhanced demand for more patient friendly and compliant dosage forms. As a result, the demand for developing new technologies has been increasing day by day. Since the development cost of a new drug molecule is very high, efforts are now being made by pharmaceutical companies to focus on the development of new drug dosage forms for existing drugs with improved safety and efficacy together with reduced dosing frequency, and the production of more cost effective dosage form.¹ Many patients, difficult to swallow tablets and hard gelatin capsules and thus do not comply with prescriptions. These results in high incidence of noncompliance and ineffective therapy.² These tablets are expected to dissolve or disintegrate in the oral cavity without drinking water. The disintegrated mass can be slide down smoothly along the esophagus with the help of saliva, so even people who have swallowing or chewing difficulties can take it with ease. The proper choice of superdisintegrants and its consistency of performance are of critical importance to the formulation development of fast dispersible tablets³. The objective of the present study is to develop fast dispersible tablets of Citalopram hydrobromide and to study the effect of functionally differences of superdisintegrants on the tablet properties as well as to improve the patient compliance without compromising the therapeutic efficacy.

Citalopram hydrobromide (Cp) is belongs to the class of SSRI (Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors) drug but it is chemically unrelated to tricyclic, tetracyclic depressants. This inhibits CNS neuronal uptake of serotonin (5HT) and used as an adjuvant in the treatment of depression and anxiety disorders. However, the high solubility, it is rapidly and extensively absorbed after oral administration and the absolute bioavailability of the drug is approximately 80% due to extensive an hepatic metabolism.⁴ Among the various techniques are used to formulate orally disintegrating tablets or fast dissolving tablets.⁵ The direct compression technique, one of the easy and fast production techniques requires the incorporation of a superdisintegrants into the formulation the use or highly water soluble excipients to achieve fast tablet disintegration was measured. In this technique does not require using water or heat during the formulation and is the ideal method for moisture and heat-labile medications. Which may be prevented and make 100% Bioavailability, the FDDS may be obtained. In the present study, an attempt was made to develop fast dispersible tablets of Citalopram hydrobromide using different superdisintegrants for its suitability to improve its bioavailability and their physicochemical characterization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: Citalopram Hydrobromide was a gift sample from Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (Hyderabad, India). Crosscarmellose sodium used was analytical grade procured from Micro Labs Pvt. Ltd. (Bangalore, India). Crospovidone and Sodium Starch Glycolate used were procured from Hetero Drugs Pvt. Ltd. (Hyderabad, India). All other reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of fast dispersible tablets of Citalopram Hydrobromide

Fast dispersible tablets containing 10mg of Citalopram were prepared by direct compression method and the various formulae used in the study are shown in table 1. All the ingredients were mixed uniformly without magnesium stearate followed by the addition of magnesium stearate. The prepared powder blends were evaluated for various parameters like bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, compressibility index and Hausner ratio. After found suitability of the powder blend, the tablets were compressed using ten-station rotary punch- tableting machine (Rimek mini Press-1) using 8mm oval punches set.

Evaluation of powder blends ^{6,9}

Bulk density

Apparent bulk density (ρ_b) was determined by placing resieved drug excipients blend into a graduated cylinder and measuring the volume (V_b) and weight (M) “as it is”using the formula below

$$\rho_b = M/V_b$$

Tapped density

The measuring cylinder containing a known mass of blend was tapped for a fixed number of taps. The minimum volume (V_t) occupied in the cylinder and the weight (M) of the blend was measured. The tapped density (ρ_t) was calculated using the formula below,

$$\rho_t = M/ V_t$$

Angle of repose

Angle of repose (α) was determined using funnel method. The blend was poured through a funnel that can be raised vertically until a maximum cone height (h) was obtained. The radius of the heap (r) was measured and angle of repose was calculated, using the formula below

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

Compressibility index

The simplest way of measurement of free flow property of powder is compressibility, an indication of the ease with which a material can be induced to flow is given by % compressibility which was calculated as follows:

$$C = (\rho_t - \rho_b) / \rho_t \times 100$$

ρ_t - Tapped density, ρ_b - Untapped bulk density

Hausner's ratio

Hausner's ratio is an index of ease of powder flow; it was calculated by using the formula below

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \rho_t / \rho_b$$

ρ_t - Tapped density, ρ_b - Untapped bulk density

Evaluation of Citalopram fast dispersible tablets¹⁰

All the tablets were evaluated for different parameters as hardness, friability, drug content, wetting time, *In vitro* dispersion time, and *In vitro* dissolution study.

Weight variation test¹¹

Weight variation test was done by weighing 20 tablets individually, by using Sartorius balance (Model CP-224-S). Calculating the average weight and comparing the individual tablet weight to the average weight.

Tablet thickness¹²

The thickness was measured by placing tablet between two arms of the Vernier Calipers. 5 tablets were taken and their average thickness was measured.

Tablet hardness¹³

The tablet hardness, which is the force required to break a tablet in a diametric compression force. The hardness tester used in the study was Monsanto hardness tester, which applies force to the tablet diametrically with the help of an inbuilt spring.

Tablet friability¹⁴

The friability of the tablet was measured in a roche friabilator. Tablets of a know weight (W_o) or a sample of 20 tablets are dedusted in a drum for a fixed time (100 revolutions) and weighed (W) again. Percentage friability was calculated from the loss in weight by following the equation given below. The weight loss should not be more than 1% and the determination was made in triplicate.

$$F = (1 - W_o/W) \times 100$$

Drug content

10 tablets were powdered and the blend equivalent to 100 mg of Citalopram was weighed and dissolved in suitable quantity of phosphate buffer of pH (6.8). The solution was filtered, suitably diluted and the drug content was analyzed spectroscopically at 240 nm. Each sample was analyzed in triplicate.

Wetting time

A piece of tissue paper (10.75×12 mm folded twice) was placed in a culture dish (d=6.5 cm) containing 6 ml of water complete wet. A tablet was placed on the wetted tissue paper and the time taken (seconds) for complete wetting of the tablet (till top) was measured.

Table 1: Formulation of Citalopram Hydrobromide tablets (Superdisintegrant method)

Ingredients	CP1	CP2	CP3	CP4	CP5	CP6	CP7	CP8	CP9	CP10	CP11	CP12
Citalopram	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10			
Crospovidone	7.5	10	12.5									
Crosscarmellose sodium				7.5	10	12.5						
Sodium starch glycolate							7.5	10	12.5			
Povidone + Crosscarmellose										5+5	7.5+2.5	2.5+7.5
Aspartame	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Mannitol	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28
M.C.C(q.s)	42.5	40	37.5	42.5	40	37.5	42.5	40	37.5	42.5	40	37.5
Lactose	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Magnesium stearate	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

***In- vitro* dispersion time**

Tablet was dropped in a beaker contain 100 ml of phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.8) at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ maintained.

The time required for complete dispersion of the tablet was noted.

Table 2: Pre compression parameter's data for Citalopram HBr powder blend

Formulation code	Angle of repose*	Loose bulk density (gm/cm ³)*	Tapped bulk density (gm/cm ³)*	Carr's Index (%)*	Hauner's ratio
CP1	24.37 \pm 0.656	0.428 \pm 0.007	0.488 \pm 0.008	12.29 \pm 0.070	1.112
CP2	25.28 \pm 0.546	0.443 \pm 0.006	0.514 \pm 0.004	13.81 \pm 0.298	1.115
CP3	23.24 \pm 0.547	0.434 \pm 0.002	0.495 \pm 0.012	12.32 \pm 0.005	1.198
CP4	25.24 \pm 0.565	0.430 \pm 0.006	0.480 \pm 0.005	10.41 \pm 0.099	1.141

CP5	23.44 \pm 0.456	0.442 \pm 0.016	0.519 \pm 0.008	14.83 \pm 0.088	1.161
CP6	24.00 \pm 0.565	0.439 \pm 0.007	0.494 \pm 0.014	11.13 \pm 0.098	1.175
CP7	25.12 \pm 0.423	0.440 \pm 0.010	0.498 \pm 0.012	13.20 \pm 0.092	1.125
CP8	23.31 \pm 0.457	0.441 \pm 0.011	0.493 \pm 0.015	12.30 \pm 0.090	1.161
CP9	24.12 \pm 0.545	0.438 \pm 0.008	0.510 \pm 0.007	14.12 \pm 0.090	1.171
CP10	24.70 \pm 0.34	0.431 \pm 0.010	0.501 \pm 0.002	13.60 \pm 0.087	1.123
CP11	23.00 \pm 0.88	0.442 \pm 0.045	0.495 \pm 0.006	13.00 \pm 0.089	1.145
CP12	23.50 \pm 0.12	0.441 \pm 0.017	0.500 \pm 0.005	13.35 \pm 0.090	1.127

* The values represent mean \pm SD, n = 3.

Table 3: Evaluation of Citalopram FDT

Parameters	CP1*	CP2*	CP3*	CP4*	CP5*	CP6*
Hardness (kg/cm)	2.5 \pm 0.2	2.7 \pm 0.3	3.0 \pm 0.2	2.5 \pm 0.2	2.7 \pm 0.3	3.0 \pm 0.2
Friability (%)	0.44 \pm 0.04	0.41 \pm 0.03	0.42 \pm 0.02	0.34 \pm 0.04	0.31 \pm 0.03	0.32 \pm 0.03
Uniformity of weight(mg)	100.56 \pm 4.4	100.67 \pm 5.2	100.32 \pm 4.2	99.56 \pm 4.4	100.0 \pm 5.5	98.32 \pm 4.2
Drug content (%)	99.65 \pm 1.5	99.34 \pm 1.4	98 \pm 2.5	99.65 \pm 1.5	99.34 \pm 1.4	98 \pm 2.5
Thickness (mm)	3.09 \pm 0.04	3.15 \pm 0.03	3.12 \pm 0.02	3.19 \pm 0.04	3.15 \pm 0.03	3.14 \pm 0.02
<i>In vitro</i> dispersion time (sec)	30 \pm 4.12	31 \pm 3.5	30 \pm 3.03	30 \pm 0.9	32 \pm 0.12	31 \pm 0.56
% Drug release after (10 min)	94.00 \pm 0.52	95.58 \pm 0.21	96.80 \pm 0.34	94.02 \pm 0.24	96.05 \pm 0.34	96.30 \pm 0.41

* The values represent mean \pm SD, n = 3.

Parameters	CP7*	CP8*	CP9*	CP10*	CP11*	CP12*
Hardness (kg/cm)	2.5 \pm 0.2	2.4 \pm 0.3	2.2 \pm 0.2	2.5 \pm 0.2	2.6 \pm 0.3	2.7 \pm 0.2

Friability (%)	0.50±0.04	0.53±0.03	0.52±0.02	0.31±0.04	0.32±0.06	0.30±0.03
Uniformity of weight(mg)	100.5±4.4	100.67±5.2	100.32±4.2	97.56±4.4	99.50±1.4	98.80±2.5
Drug content (%)	99.34±1.4	99.34±1.4	98±2.5	98.85±1.5	99.50±1.4	98.80±2.5
Thickness (mm)	3.19±0.04	3.15±0.03	3.18±0.02	3.05±0.04	2.90±0.03	3.00±0.01
<i>In vitro</i> dispersion time (sec)	30±4.12	28±3.5	30±3.03	28±0.9	24±0.12	27±0.56
% Drug release after (10 min)	96.45±0.24	96.40±0.49	95.19±0.12	95.16±0.34	95.10±0.75	93.50±0.27

The values represent mean ± SD, n = 3.

***In- vitro* dissolution study¹⁵**

The release rate of Citalopram from fast dispersible tablet was determined using LABINDIA dissolution testing apparatus II (paddle method). The dissolution test was performed using 900 ml of phosphate buffer solution (pH6.8) as a dissolution medium, at 37±1°C and 50 rpm. A sample (5ml) of the solution was withdrawn from the dissolution apparatus at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 min. The sample was filtered through whatman filter paper (0.45µ). Absorbance of these solutions was measured at 240 nm using a Systronics UV Visible spectrophotometer after appropriate dilutions. Cumulative percentage of drug release was calculated from the standard calibration curve.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

FTIR spectra were obtained on a Sipra Lab Ltd. Samples were prepared in kbr disks (2 mg sample in 200 mg KBr). The scanning range was 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹ and the resolution was 1 cm⁻¹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The powder blend for all formulation containing various concentration of crospovidone, croscarmellose sodium, sodium starch glycolate as superdisintegrant was prepared and then the FTIR studies were done that suggests incompatibility (Fig-4), the study suggests that the drug and excipients are compatible to each other. The tablets were prepared by direct compression using with a ten-station rotary punch- tableting machine (Rimek mini Press-1) using 8mm oval punches set. For each formulation, blend of drug excipients was prepared and evaluated for micromeritics properties shown in table 2. Bulk density was found to be between 0.425 to 0.445 gm/ml and tapped density between 0.480 to 0.520 gm/ml for all formulations. Hausner's ratio was found below 1.0 to 1.3 and Carr's compressibility index between 10.40 to 14.14 for all formulations. The angle

repose is known to be a measure good flow properties of powder. All batches of the tablets were evaluated for various physical parameters shown in table 3. The weight variations of all the tablets were within the range of 98.32 to 100.67 mg. The hardness of the tablets was within the range of 2.2 to 3.0 kg/cm². The friability of all tablets below 1% and the dispersion time was found Crosscarmellose sodium ≤ Crospovidone ≤ Sodium starch glycolate. The drug release increased with increased

Fig. 1: *In vitro* dissolution graphs of CP1 to CP12

Fig. 2: FTIR spectra of Citalopram (Hbr) (A) Crosscarmellose sodium, (B) Crospovidone (C) Citalopram Hydrobromide, (D) Citalopram+ All (E) Sodium starch glycolate

Stability study of CP 6

Physical parameters	Optimized formulation (CP 6)			
	0 days	15days	30days	45days
Surface Changes	NC	NC	NC	NC
Percentage drug content*	99.5±4.2	99±4.2	99±4.0	98.5±6.8
In vitro dissolution (%)*	96.30±0.47	96±0.56	95±0.50	95±0.54
Disintegration time(sec) *	18±0.56	18±0.56	18±0.56	19±0.12
Hardness (Kg) *	2.8±0.2	2.8±0.2	2.8±0.2	2.8±0.2

The values represent mean ± SD, n = 3.

NC = no change

in the level of superdisintegrants. Out of 12 formulations CP6 formulation shows best drug release 96.30±0.41% within 5 minutes.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that disintegration time and dissolution rate of Citalopram hydrobromide can be enhanced to a great extent by direct compression technique with the addition of superdisintegrants. Further investigation is needed to confirm the *in vivo* efficiency.

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